

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION'S LANGUAGE PROGRAMS FOR PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 22

Issue 10

Pages: 1128-1142

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2127

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13182406

Manuscript Accepted: 07-01-2024

Implementation of the Department of Education's Language Programs for Public Elementary Schools

Rustum D. Geonzon*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study assessed the extent of implementation of DepEd's language programs in the elementary schools in the Division of Samar as basis for a learning and development scheme. This study used the descriptive-correlation method of research. The respondents of the study were 282 elementary school heads, and 282 teachers of elementary schools in the Division of Samar. Frequency counts, percentages, means, Pearson r , Eta Correlation and t-test test for independent samples were the statistical tools used. Likewise, to treat the qualitative data derived from the focus group discussion (FGD), Nvivo application was utilized. The teacher respondents in this study, as well as the elementary school heads, perceived that two (2) of the DepEd's language programs were fully implemented. These were MTB-MLE with a mean of 4.56 (teachers') and 4.51 (school heads'); and ELLN with a mean of 4.50 (teachers') and 4.21 (school heads'). In the correlations established between the school heads profile variables and their perceptions on language program implementation not one was significantly related. There was a significant relationship between the teachers' and school heads' perceptions on the extent of implementation of language programs. On the issues and challenges encountered by school heads on the implementation of DepEd's language programs the following themes emerged: language programs not properly implemented or introduced, no appropriate training for teachers, no monitoring and evaluation of the programs, language and other programs overlap, and lack of instructional materials.

Keywords: *language programs, public elementary schools, learning and development scheme*

Introduction

The emphasis placed on acquiring another language especially English has tremendously increased and it is never futile to have it prioritized in the school curriculum where the Philippine educational system is not exempted. As reported by the Department of Education's Bureau of Educational Assessments (BEA), it is an alarming situation in the field of English language instruction to notice the 48.72% mean percentage score (MPS) in English in the National Achievement Test conducted to Grade Seven students in 2018. This examination result is far from the national planning standard of 75% so this has been brought to the attention of language policy makers and key officials in the Department of Education. While several attempts to further improve the performance and/or achievement in the English language embedded in the curricular reform of the K to 12 curriculum, it can be concluded that programs and projects in language have not been effective intervention schemes to augment student's performance in English. This is the premier situation that initially prompted this researcher to delve into this research study and likewise, this paved the way for him to go into deeper analysis on how this connects to the pursuit of the language programs in the on-going enhanced basic education curriculum that DepEd dubbed as K to 12.

Viewing more intricately at the Philippines K to 12 languages curriculum, Ocampo (2016) emphasized that, it is this curriculum that spells out the primary importance of the English language and further postulated that language is essential because it serves as the basis of all communication and it is the primary instrument of thought. Thinking, learning, and language are interrelated. Moreover, Ocampo claims that, as language is governed by rules and systems (language conventions) which are used to explore and communicate meaning, it also defines culture which is essential in understanding oneself (personal identity), forming interpersonal relationships (socialization), extending experiences, reflecting on thought and action, and contributing to a better society. Language, therefore, is central to the peoples' intellectual, social and emotional development and has an essential role in all key learning areas.

This researcher is in firm belief that, with the surge of this new curriculum that has now been implemented nationwide by the Department of Education in this country, this language teaching philosophy and rationale stated in the preceding paragraph has started to be adhered to. With this philosophy further elucidating that language is the foundation of all human relationships, it becomes an established fact that the ability of people to communicate effectively with each other owes much from this supposition. Moreover, it could thereby be expressed in this premise that this process allows students to understand better the world in which they live in, and contribute to the development of their personal perspectives of the global community. In addition, people use language to make sense of and bring order to their world. It could therefore be a must to pound on proficiency in the language as this enables them to access, process and keep abreast of information, to engage with the wider and more diverse communities, and to learn about the role of language in their own lives, and in their own and other cultures.

In the Division of Samar, all elementary school heads need to gear up in their job as language programs managers at their levels because results of the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) as reflected in the Samar Division's reading profile of grades 4 to 6 pupils where, only 35% of the total population are independent readers, only 48% are in the instructional level, and 17% are in the frustration level. This assessment results scenario also prompted this researcher to look into how elementary school heads are

performing this task of managing in the implementation of the language programs.

The foregoing contentions have been based on the experience of the researcher as the focal person in implementing the DepEd's language programs of Every Child-A-Reader Program (ECARP), Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTBMLE), Early Language, Literacy and Numeracy (ELLN), Developmentally Appropriate Practices in Early Language, Literacy and Numeracy (DAP-ELLN), and Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) at the division level. The assessment data cited earlier in this paragraph, and the meager turn out of results of other classroom-based language assessments and quarterly examinations reported as MPS in English and MTBMLE learning areas are enough indicators that have been considered in framing the backbone of this research. In addition, this current study is likewise geared towards shedding light on how best elementary school heads are expected to manage the implementation of language programs.

In this study, the researcher aims to contribute to Psychology and Education by determining the level of implementation of Language Programs and its underlying issues and concern in the Schools Division of Samar.

Research Questions

This study assessed the implementation of the Department of Education's language programs in the elementary schools in the Division of Samar. This study sought to answer the following specific questions:

1. What is the profile of the elementary school heads in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. educational attainment;
 - 1.4. field of specialization;
 - 1.5. position/status of appointment;
 - 1.6. length of service as school head; and
 - 1.7. trainings in language programs management?
2. What is the profile of the school in terms of:
 - 2.1. school population;
 - 2.2. number of teachers; and
 - 2.3. type of school?
3. What is the extent of implementation of the following language programs as assessed by the teachers and the school heads?
 - 3.1. Every Child-A-Reader Program (ECARP)
 - 3.2. Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE)
 - 3.3. Early Language, Literacy and Numeracy (ELLN)
 - 3.4. Developmentally Appropriate Practices in Early Language Literacy and Numeracy (DAP-ELLN)
 - 3.5. Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI)
4. Is the extent of implementation of language programs related to the profile of the:
 - 4.1. school head; and
 - 4.2. school?
5. Is there a difference in the perceptions of teachers and school heads on the extent of implementation of the language programs?
6. What issues and challenges were encountered by the school heads and teachers in the implementation of the identified language programs?
7. What intervention scheme may be designed based on the data that were yielded by this study?

Literature Review

Language Programs

DepEd has evolved programs in language intended to serve as vehicles in achieving its goals of developing and/or producing multi-literate individuals who could be capable to communicate/interact effectively and make meanings through language. The overarching language program of DepEd is Every Child a Reader Program (ECARP) considered as the national program that addresses the thrust of the Department of Education to make every Filipino child a reader at his/her own grade level. This program is also designed to equip elementary pupils with strategic reading and writing skills to make them independent young readers and writers. This is legitimized by DepEd Order No. 15, series of 2012 whose program components include the following:

Implementation includes the following intervention activities that have been funded: acquisition of children's story books; training of implementers (school heads and teachers; setting up a school reading center; and, advocacy that may include conferences and meetings with stakeholders, among others.

Monitoring and evaluation of ECARP shall be periodically done to ensure that implementation of the Early Reading Intervention (ERI) intended to assist readers at risk. ECARP shall also support the development/enhancement, administration and treatment, and reporting

of data obtained from reading assessment that the DepEd shall endorse. Specifically, ECARP shall support the conduct of the specific activities under each major step: development/enhancement of reading assessment designs and tools. ECARP shall venture on the localization of standardized Early Grades Reading Assessment (EGRA) to be able to obtain valid and reliable data on children's reading achievement. Localization shall entail redevelopment of EGRA in mother tongues. ECARP will fund the continuous enhancement/improvement of its home-grown reading assessment: Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) which may include review and redevelopment as well as development of relevant texts for informal reading inventory; administration of reading assessment; reading assessments data treatment and reporting. ECARP shall support the treatment of assessment data as well as the enhancement of existing data-base reporting of the Phil-IRI or development of reporting mechanisms by other reading assessments specifically the EGRA. Moreover, ECARP mainly ensures that every child is a successful reader at the end of Grade 3 and that no pupil will be promoted to the next higher grade unless he/she manifests mastery of the basic literacy skills in a particular grade level. Ensuring that all possible means of assistance and encouragement shall be extended to enable the child to read needs a skillful teacher and a supportive school head.

K to 12 curriculum believes that reading should start with the child's mother tongue (local language – the language he learned as he started to talk). In support of ECARP, Mother Tongue-Based-Multilingual Education (MTBMLE) was crafted. This was based on DepEd Order No. 74, series of 2009, and issued mandating that starting School Year 2012-2013, MTBMLE shall be implemented in all public schools, specifically in Kindergarten, Grades 1, 2 and 3 as part of the K to 12 Basic Education Program. This had been designed and implemented to make the home language of the child as the language and medium of instruction of first four grade levels in school. It is also a learning area like English, Science, etc., from Grades 1 to 3. The program components of MTBMLE include the following: advocacy work and community mobilization; development of a working orthography of the local language; multilingual education orientation and teachers training; developing, printing and distributing teachers'/facilitators guides; reading materials and other instructional materials; development of assessment tools; and evaluation and monitoring of learning outcomes.

The Early Grades Reading Assessment (EGRA) is given to randomly-selected pupils from kindergarten to grade 3 for purposes of evaluating learning outcomes of the program. Moreover, this program also ensures that reading will start with the child's native language and will be used by beginning readers as a tool in learning the two other languages (Filipino and English) considered as school languages.

Other programs include the Early Language, Literacy and Numeracy (ELLN), legitimized by DepEd Order No. 12, series 2015 issued April 10, 2015, this was issued in line with one of former President Aquino's Ten Point Agenda which stated that "every child should be a reader by grade 1." This program is aimed at strengthening its reading program through the implementation of the ELLN. The program components are as follow: establishment of baseline data (e.g., teacher and pupils' profile, language used by learners, existing and functional reading and literacy program, and support mechanisms at the ground level); materials development; development of classroom-based (formative) assessment protocol for literacy and numeracy skills; and, professional development of teachers and school heads. The Early Language Numeracy Assessment (ELNA) is given to grade 3 pupils for purposes of evaluating learning outcomes of the program. Furthermore, to cascade the continuing professional development of teachers, a two-hour School-Based Learning Action Cell (SLAC) is conducted every second and last Fridays of the month. The SLAC is needs-based as the topic facilitated by a lead teacher is based on the common findings gathered by the school heads during class observations. Number of SLACs conducted is also monitored by the division office where after completion reports (ACRs) are submitted to the focal person in the ELLN program.

Developmentally-Appropriate Practices in Early Language, Literacy and Numeracy (DAP-ELLN) is the program that aims to develop literacy and numeracy skills and attitudes among Filipino children which will contribute to lifelong learning. In connection, a series of trainings have been conducted nationwide to provide teachers updated and more effective strategies in teaching beginning reading and numeracy skills. The components are the following: design of teaching-learning activities that are age appropriate, individually appropriate, and socially and culturally appropriate; development of pupils' oral language; design of classroom-based assessment. Recent national trainings conducted last year has already touched on inclusive education considering that learners with special educational needs have started to be mainstreamed in the classroom. Evaluation of the program outcomes is done through the conduct of the Multi-Factored Assessment Tool (MFAT) where grade one pupils who are not at level – either above or below their grade levels are subjected to this one-one assessment that normally takes four (4) hours to finish.

The Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) is an assessment program revised and redesigned by the Department issued through DepEd Order No. 14, series of 2018, issued March 26, 2018. This assessment program is in support of ECARP and shall be administered to learners in public elementary schools nationwide effective school year 2018-2019. The program components include the following: administration of the Group Screening Test (GST); identification of the grades 4 to 6 pupils whose scores are 14 and below in the 14-item GST; administration of the one-on-one assessments using the graded passages; determination of the common reading miscues; and, classification of readers into independent, instructional and frustration levels; and, construction of an intervention program/scheme. Furthermore, this is used as a classroom-based assessment tool aimed at measuring and describing the learners' reading performance in both English and Filipino languages in oral reading, silent reading and listening comprehension. These three types of assessments aimed to determine the learner's independent, instructional and frustration levels in reading that provide data in creating the school reading profile. These program evaluates language p[erformance of pupils in all elementary schools in Samar Division where learners are mainly diverse in their home environment and culture, styles of coping in their school work, and in

individual motivations in learning a second language like English which I used in making sense with the world of print existing in the learners' heritage language and environment.

Summer Institute of Linguistics (SIL) of the United States, in 2018, advocates that language management is a discipline that consists of satisfying the needs of people who speak multiple different languages like the Philippines. These may be in the same country, in companies, and in cultural or international institutions where one must use multiple languages. In the Philippine context, it has been K to 12's goal to produce multilingual and multiliterate individuals after schooling and this becomes apparent SIL's advocacy.

Managing language development initiatives include: a management philosophy that guides the choice of best practices for language development programs. Management says Marmor (2017) is an art of getting things done through and with the people in formally organized groups. It is an art of creating an environment in which people can perform and individuals can co-operate towards attainment of group goals. Language program management, the main concern of this investigation, intends to look at structures and methods for a community to plan and execute projects that contribute to their language-related goals. In addition, producing individuals who could speak in their mother tongue, in their national language, and in the international language is the main goal of the languages curriculum in this country. Furthermore, language development involves many different stakeholders: local communities, civic groups, governments, educational institutions, religious organizations, plus national and international organizations.

An effective program, (SIL:2018) enlarges a community's capacity for managing the use of the languages in their current repertoire. This involves training members of the community for various roles in language development programs, including leadership development, and discovering resources to sustain program activities. With so many different goals and objectives, good management is essential to achieving the desired results through a language development program. Language program managers use these principles to: enable members of the language community to work effectively with national, local or international organizations interested in various aspects of development in the region, facilitate effective participation by those who are interested in language development results develop community and stakeholder capacity for sustainable language development including discovering resources for local project operations. Moreover, language program management in SIL builds on the experiences of its staff and the experience of other organizations who are working with communities in many parts of the world. SIL develops reference materials and provides language program management training. These contributions add to a growing body of knowledge and best practices about managing language development projects.

Implementation Concerns of Language Programs

In the Philippine context, Roxas (2016) conducted a study of Grade 1 pupils' reading difficulties in Banican where she attempted to look at the factors that affect the reading performance of Grade I pupils in cognitive development and social behaviors. The research intended to determine possible remedies that the school can implement to improve the reading and comprehension difficulty of the pupils. Roxas found out in her research that there were many ways in which teachers can help children to develop an interest in reading. One way was to make reading attractive to children by reading using ICT to support and improve learning of Grade I pupils. Teachers, Roxas further cited, must be prepared to guide children in selecting books which they are capable of reading and which they enjoy in using ICT. Using ICT could clearly be effective in improving pupils' performance in the ways described in this research. Many pupils enjoy using computers and one benefit of computers could be the combination of such motivation and the increased practice at particular tasks. Computers could therefore help by increasing the amount of time pupils, spend on particular activities, by increasing pupils motivation and engagement when doing these activities and by providing practice at an appropriate level.

There is evidence that using ICT for reading performance skills are used from a wide range of studies including simple programs with particular focus such as learning alphabets, beginning, middle and ending sounds and words, phonemic awareness, interactive educational videos, educational games, songs, numbers, shapes and learning lessons in every subject that the teachers would teach in which have all improved pupil attainment.

In Batangas Province in CALABARZON, Aguila, et. al., (2017) conducted a study on assessment of reading comprehension skills of grade 5 pupils in Conde Elementary School. The researchers wanted to assess the reading comprehension skills of pupils in terms of critical, integrative, interpretative and literal level of reading. They also wanted to determine if pupils encounter trouble in decoding and recognizing words in the text. The findings revealed that, the pupil-respondents found difficulties in interpretative, critical analysis and integrative level of reading comprehension. Using the descriptive method of research, the researchers further noted that pupils really find difficulty in analyzing and interpreting the materials they read. They suggested that different reading activities and exercises should be employed to teach students explicit reading strategies and promote higher level of thinking skills.

This study has similar intent with the one conducted by Aguila, et.al., as all of the DepEd language programs mentioned here involve the development and assessment of comprehension skills.

Ablay (2017) who investigated the status of implementation of MTBMLE in Eastern Samar and its relationship to the academic achievement of grade 3 pupils in central and non-central schools in four domains of: area of focus, teaching-learning process, teachers' training and development and preparation of learning resources, teachers and school heads perceived MTBMLE as 'moderately implemented.' She also found out that the three very serious problems encountered by the teachers and school heads both in central and non-central schools on the implementation of MTBMLE are: use of English language during contests, lack of mother tongue

vocabulary in translating highly technical terms especially in Science and Mathematics, and the absence of a dictionary in the dialect. These problems were considered moderately serious by both teachers and school heads. The researcher concluded that there is a need to conduct training programs to ensure professional growth of the teachers and school heads. Teachers need to be properly oriented, trained and supervised in the implementation of the MTBMLE program and that construction and utilization of MTBMLE materials be like books and other instructional materials be conducted.

This study of Ablay is closely related to the present one as both intend to address issues on proper implementation of the MTBMLE program of the DepEd. While Ablay's study focused on one program – MTBMLE, this present study looks into five major language programs of DepEd. Also, Ablay's study found out that MTBMLE is moderately implemented in the Division of Eastern Samar, and this present one yielded data to support that it is fully implemented in the Division of Samar. The differences in perception could be attributed to the kind of language management practices employed by the focal persons in this program.

Apacible (2016) had conducted another study on mother tongue-based instruction in Leyte division. He was concerned on determining the effect of mother-tongue based instruction on the reading performance in English of grade 4 pupils in Leyte division. After undergoing the research, he was led to land up into the conclusions that pupils who had MTBMLE experience had word recognition of instructional level as opposed to those without MTBMLE experience whose word recognition was at frustration level. But both groups of pupils were at the frustration level in reading comprehension and the levels of academic performance was satisfactory. Meanwhile, the pupils' academic performance was related to their reading performance along word recognition and reading comprehension. There was also relationship between the pupils' academic performance and their profile variables.

Looking at both Apacible's work and this present study, it could be said that MTBMLE has an impact on pupils reading and academic performance. The similarities of both studies were in the implementation of the MTBMLE as one of the language programs of DepEd.

Finally, in the Philippine context specifically in the island of Samar, Irene (2015), who conducted a case study on the best practices in instructional leadership of secondary school administrators, noted that in terms of best practices in instructional leadership majority of the school administrators in Samar belonged to the top performing schools and tend to practice always clarifying a vision; creating a healthy school environment; cultivating leadership in others; and improving instruction and managing people, data and process.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used the mixed-method research to describe the profile of the elementary school heads and the schools they managed, and the extent of implementation of the Department of Education's language programs in the Division of Samar. This was part of the quantitative data that this study determined. Likewise, quantitative data was used to further describe the profile of schools from where the school heads and teacher-respondents came. This study further delved into the perceptions of both teachers and school heads on how the Department of Education's language programs were implemented. In addition, the descriptive method was considered appropriate in this investigation as it helped the researcher ascertain the extent of the relationships between and amongst the variables that this study looked into. Meanwhile, to investigate the issues and challenges encountered by elementary school heads and teachers, focus group discussions (FGDs) were conducted to three groups: school heads, central school teachers, and non-central school teachers. The transcribed proceedings of the FGDs containing the responses and reactions of the respondents from the questions prepared by this researcher, formed part of the qualitative data.

Participants

Out of the 662 public elementary schools in the Division of Samar, this study was conducted using only 50% of the total number of schools particularly two hundred eighty-two (282) elementary school heads who turned up during the actual fielding of the research instruments as some school heads were attending the orientation-workshop for poll chairmen and poll clerks for the 2019 elections. Of the 282 school heads, 28 or 9.93% came from central schools while 254 or 90.07% were school heads of non-central schools. Same with the teacher-respondents where two hundred eighty-two (282) teachers actually participated in the fielding of the instruments. Of the 282 teachers, 87 or 30.85% were central school teachers while 195 or 69.14% were non-central elementary school teachers. Using the Slovin's formula of $n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$, these samples were derived. This formula could be explained as n was the desired samples taken from N which was the total population/universe divided by 1 plus population's square of the margin of error. During the focus group discussions (FGDs), 45 participants were derived from the total population through random sampling: 15 were elementary school heads; 15 were central school teachers; and, 15 were non-central school teachers.

Instruments

This study utilized two (2) researcher-made questionnaires for the respondents who were elementary school heads and teachers of the Division of Samar during school year 2018-2019. The first questionnaire was for the school heads and the elementary school teachers, and the second was the FGD guide that was used by the researcher during the actual FGDs.

The teachers and school heads questionnaire contained the following parts. Part I asked the data on the profile variables of the school heads which included age, sex, educational attainment, field of specialization, length of service as school head, position/appointment,

and, language programs management trainings attended in the past five years. It was also in this part where the following school data were asked: school population, number of teachers, and school type.

Part II of the researcher-made questionnaires elicited data on the implementation of DepEd's language programs in elementary schools in the Division of Samar for the elementary school heads and same part for the questionnaires of the teacher respondents. This part used the five-point Likert Scale to assess the teachers and school heads' perspectives on the extent of implementation of the DepEd's language programs which were part of the variables of the study. Part III of the researcher-made questionnaire was the FGD/interview guide composed of 5 questions used during the Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) by the FGD moderator.

The Survey Questionnaires were pilot tested in the Schools Division of Catbalogan City while the semi-structured interview guide by language expert in the Schools Division of Samar.

Procedure

The dry-run and the fielding of the research instruments needed the permission of the Schools Division Superintendent. Hence, this researcher sought permission by writing a formal letter request. A letter request was also sent to the Public Schools District Supervisor (PSDS) assigned in the school district where the sample schools belong.

Upon getting the SDS's approval to field the questionnaire and conduct FGDs, all letter requests were forwarded to the respective schools and the accomplishment of the research instrument and the FGDs were anticipated. Distribution, administration, and retrieval of the research instruments was personally handled by the researcher. It was completed when the Phil-IRI orientation was conducted to elementary school heads and teachers. This capability building seminar gave this researcher a chance to meet the teachers and school heads. During the workshop sessions, one of the activities was a differentiated learning and delivery session that was intended to find out to what extent were the DepEd's language programs implemented and what perceptions do the teachers and school heads had on the present status of DepEd's language programs implementation. The researcher gave out the questionnaires to the groups who were randomly chosen as respondents in this study – the group of teacher-respondents and the group of elementary school heads. The groups who were not included in this research were made to create charts and other creative activities to find out answers to the same topic given with those involved in this research.

The accomplished questionnaires were collated by the researcher from the respondents – teachers and school heads. These became the data that this study utilized and analyzed. In addition, the data on profile of schools, were obtained from the division Enhanced Basic Education Information System (EBEIS) stored in the system under the charge of the division planning officer. Finally, to identify the issues and challenges of teachers and school heads in the implementation of DepEd's language programs, focus group discussions (FGDs) were made separately among the teachers and school head respondents. Specifically, 3 FGD groups were established, 1 for school heads, 1 for central school teachers and 1 for the non-central school teachers. The researcher first established the objectives of the FGD, introduced the FGD participants and asked permission to put the responses in writing all the proceeding of the FGDs. All results were transcribed later by the researcher. Some answers given by MTB-MLE teachers using the Waray language were translated into English by this researcher.

The researcher also served as moderator while a time keeper and a recorder were assigned to make sure that the FGDs would not exceed the time allotment, and the responses were properly documented and accounted for. Each of the FGDs was conducted for an hour. The FGD for school heads which was composed of randomly selected school heads, was done at the library hub of DepEd Division of Samar. The FGD for central school teachers was conducted in a casual conversation form at the SPED center of one central school. Finally, the FGD for non-central school teachers was conducted at the Alternative Learning center in another school.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher ensured that the identity of the respondent-participants was protected, their identity concealed. The responses were strictly anonymous and no personal identifying information, was collected or linked to their responses. To help protect the anonymity of the respondents, the survey did not contain information that would personally identify them. The results of this study may be published, but the researcher would not know the name and identity. No individual identifiable responses would be forwarded to any administration of the schools only aggregated data. If data from this study is to be published or presented, any information that identifies the respondents will not be included. The researcher did not force any respondent to participate in the research and their participation was voluntary as the researcher explained thoroughly the purpose of the research.

Results and Discussion

This section chapter presents the results of the study with emphasis on the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered from the instruments used by the researcher and distributed to the respondents composed of school heads and teachers in the different elementary schools in the Division of Samar.

Profile of School Heads in Terms of Age, Sex, Educational Attainment and Field of Specialization

Age

Data in Table 1 reflects that most of the elementary school heads, 102 or 36.4 percent were middle aged, 8 or 2.8 percent were 61 years old and above, described as retirement age. With a combined total of 164 or 58.16 percent of the elementary school heads were above middle-aged and fairly young with the age bracket of 31-51 years old. It could be implied that most of them may be new in their positions/designations and thereby they would still need more experiences of implementing/managing language programs. Moreover, data also show that only few of the school heads have specialized/majored in English or Filipino which could mean that there is a considerable number of school heads who need to attend learning and development sessions on language programs management to capacitate them more on this necessary skill as leaders of instruction in their respective schools. It can be further inferred that since most of them are in their middle age, they can still learn a great deal of ideas and practices in language programs management so that they can carry out their goals as school heads. Also, they can still improve themselves and learn from experience and from appropriate technical assistance from supervisors or from fellow school heads.

Sex

Table 1 further reveals that there are more female administrators than there are males at a sum of 192 or 68.1%. The truism that the teaching profession is dominated by the female gender holds true even in the context of school management. This can be attributed to the fact that, in the teaching-learning process, verbal ability is an important consideration which according to the theory on multiple intelligences, females tend to possess better linguistic intelligence than their male counterparts.

Table 1. *Profile of School Heads in Terms of Age, Sex, Educational Attainment and Field of Specialization*

Profile Variables		School Heads	
		Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Age	Retirement Age (61 years old and above)	8	2.8%
	Above Middle Age (51-60 years old)	80	28.4%
	Middle Age (41-50 years old)	102	36.4%
	Fairly Young (31-40 years old)	84	29.6%
	Young (20-30 years old)	8	2.8%
	Mean Age: 45.6383		
	Total	282	100%
Sex	Male	90	31.9%
	Female	192	68.1%
	Total	282	100%
Educational Attainment	Doctoral Degree	12	4.3%
	PhD CAR	20	7.1%
	With PhD Units	22	7.8%
	Master's Degree	60	21.3%
	MA CAR	70	24.7%
	With MA Units	86	30.5%
	Baccalaureate Degree	12	4.3%
	Total	282	100%
Field of Specialization	English	24	9.8%
	Mathematics	29	10.2%
	Science & Technology		
	ST General Science	52	18.3%
	ST Biology	8	2.8%
	ST Chemistry	27	9.6%
	ST Physics/Physical Science	2	.7%
	Filipino	14	5%
	Araling Panlipunan	8	2.8%
	Values Education	18	5.6%
	MAPEH	10	3.5%
	TLE	20	7.1%
	Home Economics	52	18.3%
	Industrial Arts	8	2.8%
	Agriculture	8	2.8%
	Entrepreneurship	2	.7%
Total	282	100%	

Educational Attainment

In this study, Table 1 presents that 86 or 30.5 percent of the respondents had MA units. This could be attributed to their young age

considering that only 22 or 30.9 (Table 2) were Teachers-In-Charge (TICs) who could be permanent Teacher I, II, or III, whose designation are renewable every year.

Majority of the school heads were certificate of academic requirements (CAR) holders for an MA degree comprising 70 or 24.7 percent. Furthermore, 60 or 21.3 percent hold an MA degree. It is noticeable from the data that there are few Principal positions considering that a Master’s degree is a requirement for a school head to occupy a Principal I item, and specific unit credits in the doctorate level to get promoted to Principal II, III, and IV.

Field of Specialization

It can be gleaned from Table 1 that more general science (52 or 18.3%) and industrial arts specialists (52 or 18.3%) have been appointed as school heads. A combined number of 53 or 21.03 percent are having specializations in English (24 or 9.8%) and Filipino (29 or 10.2%). This would imply that a great number of teachers are TLE specialists.

Profile of School Heads in Terms of Length of Service as School Head, and Language Programs Management Trainings Attended

Length of Service as School Head

It can be gleaned from Table 2 that more respondents are in their mid-career comprising 222 or 53.6 percent of the total school head respondents as opposed to the novice in length of service as school head (60 or 46.4%). It can be deduced that only few of the school heads has less experience in managing the implementation of DepEd’s language programs.

Table 2. Profile of School Heads in Terms of Length of Service as School Head, and Language Programs Management Trainings Attended

Profile Variables		School Heads	
		Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Length of Service as School Head	Mid-career (10-20 years)	222	53.6%
	Novice (1-9 years)	60	46.4%
	Total	282	100%
Position/ Status of Appointment	Principal- IV	24	8.4%
	Principal-III	24	8.4%
	Principal-II	8	2.8%
	Principal- I	30	12.7%
	Head Teacher I-VI	174	36.8%
	Teacher-In-Charge	22	30.9%
	Total	282	100%
Language Management Trainings Attended (No. of Hours)	40 and above	174	36.8%
	30-39	48	16.8%
	20-29	52	43.6%
	10-19	8	2.8%
	0-9	0	0
	Total	282	100%

Position/Status of Appointment

Table 2 reveals that most of the school heads (174 or 36.8%) are full-fledged head teachers ranging from a regular permanent appointment of Head I to Head Teacher VI.

Trainings in Language Programs Management Attended in the Last Five Years

In this study, Table 2 presents that 36.8% of the total respondents have received 40 and above hours of trainings in managing language programs’ implementation. This percentage shows that school heads had very insufficient trainings on language programs management. This could be traced further that only a considerable number of school heads were able to attend the trainings conducted by the DepEd either regional or division. It could be that these trainings especially on the management of the language programs included in this study were conducted when some of the respondents had earlier commitments, or other trainings scheduled on same dates.

Profile of Schools in Terms of School Population, Number of Teachers and Type of School

Data in Table 3 presents the number of schools that were chosen as samples in this study. It is also reflected in Table 3 that there were 282 school heads and 282 teachers involved in the study. Based on their school population otherwise reported as number of pupils enrolled for the current year, forty-eight (48) schools or 17.2% were large, one hundred and thirty (130) or 46.09% were medium schools and one hundred and four (104) or 36.88% were small schools. These data were obtained from the Enhanced Basic Education Information System (EBEIS).

As to the number of teachers assigned to teach in the sample schools, it could be further gleaned from Table 3 that forty-one (41) of the teacher respondents or 14.54% came from large schools, one hundred and forty-three (143) or 50.71% came medium schools and

ninety-eight (98) or 34.75% were from small schools.

Furthermore, in the Division of Samar, the table shows that there are twenty-nine (29) school districts therefore same number of central schools. But one central school was used in the dry run and trial of the research instruments so, in this study, twenty-eight (28) or 9.9% were from central schools and two hundred and fifty-four (254) were from non-central schools.

Table 3. *Profile of Schools in Terms of School Population, Number of Teachers and Type of School*

Profile Variables		Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
School Population	large school (600-1000+)	48	17.02%
	medium school (200-599)	130	46.09%
	small school (199-below)	104	36.88%
	Total	282	100%
Number of Teachers	large school (20 and above)	41	14.54%
	medium school (10-19)	143	50.71%
	small school (9 and below)	98	34.75%
	Total	282	100%
School Type	central school	28	9.9%
	non-central school	254	90.07%
	Total	282	100%

Central schools in the Division of Samar, being situated in the municipality, have larger enrolment and thereby more number of sections/classes and teachers, than those in the non-central schools. EBEIS further showed that non-central schools are those that are basically complete elementary schools offering kindergarten level to grade six but they differ in the following aspects: those with large enrolments where there are increased number of sections per grade level, those that are complete in grade levels with monograde classes, and, those with combination or multigrade classes.

Extent of Implementation of DepEd's Language Programs as Assessed by Teachers and School Heads

This study also looked into the perception of teachers and school heads as regards the extent of implementation of language programs. The succeeding discussions focus on the perceptions of teachers and school heads on each of the programs.

Every Child a Reader Program (ECARP)

The first DepEd language program that was assessed by the teachers and school heads who were chosen as respondents in this study is ECARP.

Table 4 shows that teacher-respondents perceived that ECARP is moderately implemented with a mean of 3.35. This would tell that not many of them have attended orientation trainings on the implementing guidelines, rules and regulations as spelled out in DepEd Order No. 45, series of 2002 otherwise known as ECARP implementing rules and guidelines. Teachers' perceptions about this language program were lower than that of the school heads.

Generally, school heads perceived ECARP as moderately implemented with a mean of 3.41. This data shows that not many of the school heads have been able to follow through the implementation of ECARP which could be inferred as they have not had enough knowledge about rules and processes on how this umbrella program in reading initiated by DepEd central office. It is also probable that most of the school heads who were respondents in this study were not yet in their positions as school heads when project ECARP was institutionalized. It could be that they were still teachers that time and as usual teachers wait for their school heads to conduct in-service trainings (INSETs) that would help them in understanding updates received from regional or national trainings.

Since ECARP was institutionalized as a premier program that caters to policies in language and reading instruction/pedagogy, this has not been evaluated yet if only to check on how this works at the school and classroom levels.

Table 4. *Extent of Implementation of the DepEd's Language Programs as Assessed by Teachers and School Heads*

Extent of Implementation of Language Programs as assessed by Teachers and School Heads	Teachers		School Heads	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
Every Child a Reader Program (ECARP)	3.35	moderately implemented	3.41	Moderately implemented
Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE)	4.56	fully implemented	4.51	fully implemented
Early Language Literacy and Literacy (ELLN)	4.50	fully implemented	4.21	almost fully implemented
Developmentally Appropriate Practices Early Language Literacy and Literacy (DAP-ELLN)	4.25	almost fully implemented	4.23	almost fully implemented
Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (PHIL-IRI)	4.34	almost fully implemented	4.41	almost fully implemented

Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTBMLE)

The MTBMLE program considered as the one that emphasizes on the "first language first" policy, was the second to be investigated in this study.

Table 4 reveals that, in the mean pegged at 4.56, teacher-respondents believed that MTBMLE as a DepEd language program was highly implemented. Their own classroom practices of using the Mother Tongue as medium of instruction and as a learning area in the curriculum would further prove that this program was fully implemented in the Division of Samar as perceived by the teacher-respondents. Moreover, it could be inferred that most of these teacher respondents had attended training-workshops and orientations on how MTBMLE works to show confidence in following the program goals, objectives, rules, guidelines and processes.

In same Table, it is reflected that school heads likewise believed that MTBMLE was fully implemented with a mean of 4.51. It is noticeable in the results that school heads have done visits in the classrooms where teachers implementing the provisions in the MTBMLE program objectives were seen. It would further be inferred that these school heads had sent their K to 3 teachers to trainings in MTBMLE so that the teachers and them could both understand the what's, whys and how's of MTBMLE and yield good results when assessments would be conducted next year.

Early Language Literacy and Numeracy (ELLN)

The program that blends literacy and numeracy is ELLN. Focusing mainly on the stages in presenting reading lessons, engaging learners in reading activities, and teaching and learning math, this ELLN program promises meaningful results when implemented properly. The ELLN program, just like MTB-MLE, had been perceived as fully implemented by the teachers with a mean of 4.50. It could be gleaned from the table that most of them had attended the ten-day mass training of teachers in ELLN conducted by the Division Office as mandated by DepEd Order No. 12, s. of 2015. This perception would show that the teacher respondents could have started revitalizing their conduct and facilitation of beginning reading instruction as among the contents of the ELLN program.

On the other side, at a mean of 4.21, school heads perceived that ELLN was fully implemented. Most of them, in tandem with their K to 3 teachers, had attended the capability building sessions on ELLN and that, they had delegated their K to 3 teachers to attend the ten-day training. In addition, this perception manifested by school heads would mean that they had internalized the program goals and objectives and that they had started to technically assist teachers in the implementation of this program.

Developmentally Appropriate Practices in ELLN (DAP-ELLN)

Implementing DAP-ELLN could ensure that lessons designed by teachers would be age, individually and culturally-appropriate. It's this program that claims that teaching materials should also be designed in same way.

Teacher respondents after having attended the training perceived that DAP-ELLN was almost convinced that this was fully implemented with a mean of 4.25. It is reflected further that developmental screening is evident in the classrooms through the use of the Early Child Care and Development (ECCD) checklist to gauge kindergarten pupils' readiness for Grade 1 instruction. Also, they had started to design their teaching-learning activities in such a way that they were age appropriate, individually appropriate, and, culturally appropriate. At the mean of 4.23, school heads perceived DAP-ELLN as fully implemented. This could be a clear indication that most of them have received and participated in trainings and workshops that taught them how this program worked with them in their own schools.

Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI)

The Phil-IRI was basically designed as classroom-based assessment tool to gauge reading performance by describing and grouping readers into independent, instructional and frustration levels. Being the only language program on assessment having English and Filipino versions, the Phil-IRI provides teachers an idea of how to design their intervention schemes in reading. Teachers perceived that this assessment program is almost fully implemented with a mean of 4.34. The respondents were further convinced that with the series of orientation-workshops this will be fully implemented by next school year. They further perceived that language assessment, say English and Filipino should be conducted so that reading intervention programs would be crafted based on the reading levels of students (independent, instructional, and frustration).

Table 4 further shows that at the mean of 4. 41, school head respondents perceived this language assessment program as almost fully implemented. They also perceived that this language assessment program needs to be managed/implemented properly/correctly to determine the levels at which students read so that acquisition of reading materials would be appropriate.

Extent of Implementation of DepEd's Language Programs and Its Relationship to Profile of School Heads

This study also determined the relationships between the extent of implementation of DepEd language programs and the profile of the school heads. In this portion the analysis of the relationships of the variables in this study is discussed.

Table 5. *Extent of Implementation of DepEd's Language Programs and their Relationships to the Profile of School Heads*

Profile	Extent of Language Program Implementation School Heads (n=282)		
	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Interpretation
Age	.017	.776	NS
Sex	-.079	.187	NS

Educational Attainment	.096	.107	NS
Field of Specialization	.081	.189	NS
Length of Service as School Head	.180	.003	S
Position/Status of Appointment	-.037	.537	NS
Trainings Attended for the Last five Years	.118	.051	NS

Legend: NS=Not Significant; S=Significant

Table 5 presents the correlation between school heads’ profile variables and the extent of implementation of language programs. It is shown that none of the profile variables was significantly related to the respondents’ perception on the extent of implementation of the language programs. Data on this table would be used to declare that the null hypothesis that says there is no significant relationship between the profile of the school heads and their perceptions on the extent of implementation of language programs was accepted.

Among the profile variables that could be gleaned from this table, respondents’ sex as well as their position/status of appointments were negatively correlated to their perceptions on the extent of implementation of the DepEd language programs.

Extent of Implementation of DepEd’s Language Programs and Its Relationship to the Profile of Schools

It was also the intent of this study to look into the extent of implementation of DepEd language programs and their relationships to the profile of schools. Table 6 reflects the correlation between the profile of schools and the extent of implementation of language programs. As shown in the table, among the following profile variables of the sample schools: school population, number of teachers and type of school, none of the school profile variables have significant relationship to the extent of implementation of language programs.

With the findings reflected on Table 5 as bases, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the profile of schools and the extent of implementation of language programs was accepted. It could be further shown in Table 5 that school population and the type of school had negative coefficient of correlation, while number of teachers were not.

Table 6. *Extent of Implementation of DepEd Language Programs and their Relationships to the Profile of Schools*

Profile	Extent of Language Program Implementation School Heads (n=282)		
	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Interpretation
School Population	-.039	.514	NS
Number of Teachers	.055	.359	NS
Type of School	-0.43	.405	NS

Legend: NS=Not Significant; S=Significant

Difference Between Teachers’ and the School Heads Perceptions on the Extent of Implementation of Language Programs

In the results mentioned earlier, it came out that no significant relationships exist between the perceptions of school heads and teachers on the extent of implementation of language programs. To expound further the relationship of variables studied, Table 7 below, presents the test of difference between the teachers’ and school heads perceptions on the extent of implementation of language programs.

It can be gleaned from Table 8 that the differences in the perceptions of teachers and school heads on the extent of implementation of language programs are highly significant. All the p-values as reflected on the table on the DepEd language programs: ECARP, MTBMLE, ELLN, DAP-ELLN and Phil-IRI are lower than the .05 alpha significance level. Based on these results, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and school heads on the extent of implementation of the DepEd language programs was rejected. Thus, a significant difference on teachers and school heads perceptions on the extent of implementation of language programs exist.

Based on these findings, since differences in the perceptions of teachers and school heads exist as computed using tests of difference, it could be inferred that the trainings and workshops on language programs’ implementation where teachers and their school heads were in attendance, have been received differently and in most cases, could be implemented differently. As supported by the data in Table 9, it can be led to a realization for focal persons that there is a dire need to check and see how DepEd language program implementers fare in the practices they have done in putting language programs in proper perspective. This could only be done through purposeful monitoring and evaluation. Finally, it could be suggested that, if and when language programs implementation is not properly heading, then it behooves school heads and focal persons, therefore, to think and afterwards model ways on how to redirect the implementation process.

Table 7. *Test of Difference in the Perceptions of Teachers and School Heads on the Extent of Implementation of DepEd’s Language Programs*

Language Programs	Mean Difference	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Every Child a Reader Program (ECARP)	.702	11.508	.000	HS
Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE)	1.436	39.75	.000	HS
Early Language Literacy and Literacy (ELLN)	1.205	24.116	.000	HS

Developmentally Appropriate Practices Early Language Literacy and Literacy (DAP-ELLN)	1.227	16.219	.000	HS
Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (PHIL-IRI)	1.454	27.726	.000	HS

Legend: HS=Highly Significant

Issues and Challenges Encountered by the School Heads and Teachers in the Implementation of DepEd's Language Programs

Presentation of the Qualitative Data from the Focus Group Discussions

This portion of the research presents the discussion of the qualitative data. The following emerged as the challenges and issues encountered by the elementary school heads and teachers. The first one was that language programs of the Department of Education were not properly implemented or introduced to them. This was one of the main reasons that the participants found it not very easy in implementing the language programs. They continued by expressing that they were not trained well to handle the programs and that they were not monitored and evaluated periodically.

The teacher respondents as well as the heads of schools said the programs were too many and they overlapped. It was difficult for them, therefore to implement the language programs because they also had to teach the competencies required of them. Finally, the FGD participants were unanimous in stating that they lacked the instructional materials that they would use in implementing the programs and these themes have the more detailed discussion in this section.

Language programs not properly implemented or introduced

Most of the FGD participants were one in saying this preceding phrase. Also, majority of the teachers admitted that most of the DepEd programs were not properly introduced to them. However, all the forty-five (45) FGD participants in the three groups manifested their willingness to be trained. Manifesting sincerity in her tone, a head teacher for seven years said:

...not all of the DepEd language programs were well-introduced to every school and in some cases teachers handling the program were not well-equipped with the comprehension or skills in the implementation. (transcript FGD transcript A, line 133.)

It could be inferred from this statement that one issue in language programs implementation in the school division, is the inability of teachers who are assigned to handle the programs to implement them with confidence because of inappropriate or even lack of training. Most of the language programs were conducted at the division level hence, it could be inferred that some trainers who were assigned to handle the training sessions were not adept at their topics or they lack facilitation skills. Unfortunately, these are the two basic criteria in choosing/identifying teacher trainers – content knowledge and facilitating knowledge. To continue further the discussion in the FGD, it was suggested by one school head to -

“intensify SLAC, reorientation of these programs needs to be done”

This was specifically said by a participant, line 17, FGD transcript A. In addition, on the part of the teacher participants there were those who said the following negative comments:

“... there were language programs that were not well-implemented in our schools because school heads did not orient us properly in the implementation. There is also a need for us to have re-orientation.”

This could be found in transcript FGD transcript C, lines 123 to 124. On the contrary, another school head expressed in the FGD transcript A by saying that:

... lack of expertise on the part of the teachers on the programs.... (line 182)

These statements that appeared like passing the buck on the issues and challenges in the implementation of language programs, corroborated with Bokhari (2015) who studied on teachers' perceptions on the implementation of literacy, numeracy and screening (LINUS) among lower primary pupils. Bokhari further stated that effectiveness of the LINUS programme depended largely on the teachers. They need to be oriented and trained to handle the programme.

No appropriate training for teachers

Connecting with statements cited in the preceding discussion, another issue that popped up in the FGD centered on appropriate training for teachers. Although 90% of the teacher participants in the FGDs were able to attend some mass trainings especially in ELLN, they were still one in saying that:

“More trainings po Sir with no registration.” (FGD transcript B, line 191)

“I feel there is a need for training.” (FGD transcript B, line 194)

“I agree, more trainings especially reading.” (FGD transcript B, line 195)

The foregoing statements which have been expressed directly by teachers vouch for the need of appropriate training in implementing

the language programs. This would conform with ELLN program's rules and provisions clarifying on the need for establishing a sustainable and cost-effective professional development for teachers. This is corroborated by Bryant (2012) in his study on instructional practices implemented by teachers who finally recommended that teachers of ELL preschoolers should receive professional development opportunities, like appropriate training, to be able to understand the developmental sequence of second language learning on the one hand, and, to further equip them with the knowledge and strategies that will provide focused English acquisition experiences for identified ELL preschoolers, on the other.

No monitoring and evaluation of the programs

Almost all of the FGD participants – school heads and teachers alike, bared out that there is a need for close monitoring and supervision, and even evaluation of language programs implementation. A teacher who has taught in the early grades for 10 years expressed by saying that –

“There should be monitoring and evaluation. Teachers should be aware on implementation status” (lines 43 and 44 in the FGD transcript B)

This could follow, therefore, that teachers are not informed on the language programs implementation status that they are doing, thereby leading them to realize that whether or not they are properly heading in programs implementation, they are not even aware of them. While DepEd presumes that the monitoring and evaluation (M & E) mechanism such as mentoring, coaching and technically assisting are in place, these statements reveal that school heads have been heading on a different focus other than performing their main task, comprising 70% of their job, which is instructional supervision.

Meanwhile, a throng of teacher participants in the FGD groups were in unison when they pointed out that that there is a need to -

“Orient the teachers, we are the prime movers of the programs, coaching and mentoring are needed. Principals should also do this” asserted by one participant in the FGD transcript C.

Furthermore, teachers from the non-central group said confidently to the FGD moderator and the entire group –

“Close monitoring of programs, please.” (FGD transcript C, line 202)

“There should be a follow-up.” (FGD transcript, B, line 155)

“Regularly monitor programs implementation (for school head and PSDS) so that suggestions are given for improvement.” (FGD transcript B, line 204)

To unearth the truth on language programs implementation practices does not surprise this researcher as reports from program implementers reveal that things have not been very well done so, drawbacks on the desired outputs which is the language performance, particularly reading, are still wanting.

Language and other programs overlap

This very interesting topic/question delved into by this researcher in the FGDs revealed how fed-up teachers and schools' heads have been with the myriad of programs to be implemented by them the entire school year. Unexpectedly, the teachers expressed sincerely what they have gone through. Aside from their concerns over the inappropriate training and program orientation, the need for support, and the lack of monitoring and evaluation, 50% of the teacher participants revealed that DepEd language programs implementation has become taxing and at times, confusing for them.

A participant, who had just been in the service for 4 years said:

“Sir, because in DepEd there are many programs. We don't have time because we are also teaching the pupils. Doing lesson plans, and many more.” (lines 26-27 in FGD transcript B).

This can be an alarming statement. The one reason that could be attributed to the decline of students' scores in the national achievement test

Other teachers disclosed:

“Overlapping language activities. (FGD transcript B, line 129)

“Although the passion is there, there are shortcomings. (FGD transcript B, line 130)

As the FGDs continued majority of the teacher participants added up the following lines/statements which they felt had happened due to overlapping of program activities:

“There is no focus.” (FGD transcript B, line 122)

“differences in priorities.” (FGD transcript B, line 123)

“Lack of time” in program implementation as the activities in the programs overlap,”(FGD transcript B, line 124)

In addition, a participant also stated that:

“Conflict of time. So many things to do in a day.”(FGD C, line 150)

“Too many school activities and too many reports on activities asked by our school head.” (FGD C, line 152)

Realizations could be that reducing the number of language programs would eventually help teachers to focus. The many activities that each of the programs advocate pose as real challenges for teachers. Furthermore, this brings to a conclusion that a promising success in language programs implementation awaits everyone in the entire DepEd school system.

Lack of instructional materials

The ultimate issue that was talked about by both teacher participants and school heads in the FGDs was the scarcity of instructional materials especially in the local language (mother tongue). Those teaching in grades 1 to 3, unanimously whined that:

“Materials in mother tongue language are not available.” (FGD transcript A, line 175)

“There is lack of resources to be utilized in the implementation at the field.” (FGD transcript A, line 177)

A primary grades teacher who has been in the for the past 9 years, joined by two other participants, had this to say:

“Lack of materials, both teaching IMs and stationeries.” (FGD transcript C, lines 136to 140)

Maybe because of lack of time in producing/writing her own stories/storybooks, a participant who had taught mother tongue since the inception of MTBMLE into the curriculum, proceeded by saying that:

“Books with story for MTBMLE are few and not available; those available are not suited to the learners on their level.” (FGD transcript C, line 154)

Underscoring these issues and challenges capped the narrowed down focus that could possibly be resorted to so that DepEd language program implementation would come to fruition. For this reason, the portion of this study would eventually help in realizing this anticipated leap.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were formulated:

School heads belonged to the age bracket of 30-50 years old and females. Majority of the school heads were full-fledged Head Teachers with MA units. Most of the respondents in this study indicated to have very insufficient trainings on implementing and managing language programs.

The profile variables of age, sex, educational attainment, length of service as school head and position held did not significantly relate to their perceptions of language programs implementation.

Trainings on language programs implementation were both needed by teachers and school heads.

There is a significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and school heads on implementation of language programs in the Schools Division of Samar.

Issues and challenges of teachers in language programs implementation varied according to the school population, number of teachers and type of school. Most of these concerns pertains to the lack of introduction or clear orientation of the language programs, overlapping of school activities, lack of instructional materials and lack of trainings for public elementary school heads and teachers and monitoring and evaluation of the language programs are not institutionalized leading deficiencies in terms of Language Programs implementation.

The profile of school heads did not significantly relate to their perceptions on the extent of implementation of language programs.

Based on the conclusions derived, the following measures are hereby recommended:

School heads should conduct a thorough School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) to orient teachers in their charge, the content and implementation procedures/guidelines on language programs implementation.

School heads should increase their number of times in classroom supervision to ensure that language programs are implemented,

Coaching and mentoring sessions should be done to newly-hired teachers so that they could handle the implementation of language programs correctly.

During trainings and workshops on language programs management, resource teachers/speakers should clarify language program goals and objectives so that teachers and school heads will be properly directed. The trainers should be well adept in their topics.

Teachers and school heads should attend capability building and learning and development sessions on language content and pedagogy. School heads and teachers should feel encouraged to enroll in graduate programs especially those about language teaching. The proposed learning and development design appended hereto should be adopted by the Division of Samar to improve teachers and school heads capabilities in implementing language programs and thereby increase the language performance of students.

References

- Ablay, R. (2017). Implementation of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTBMLE) and Academic Achievement of Pupils in the Division of Eastern Samar. Doctoral Dissertation. Eastern Visayas State University, Tacloban City.
- Apacible, A. (2016). Mother Tongue-Based Instruction and Reading Performance in English of Pupils in Leyte Division. Doctoral Dissertation. Eastern Visayas State University, Tacloban City.
- Aquino, G. V. (2001). Educational management: Principles, functions, concepts. Rex Book Store.
- Bokhari, R., Rashid, S. M., & Heng, C. S. (2015). Teachers' perception on the implementation of the literacy, numeracy and screening (LINUS LBI 2.0) programme among lower primary ESL pupils. *Malaysian Journal of ELT Research*, 11(1).
- Bryant, P. C. (2012). Instructional Practices To Support PreK English Language Learners (Doctoral dissertation, College of Saint Elizabeth).
- DepEd Order No. 14, s. 2018. Policy guidelines on the administration of the revised philippine informal reading inventory. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2018/03/26/do-14-s-2018-policy-guidelines-on-the-administration-of-the-revised-philippine-informal-reading-inventory/>
- DepEd Order No. 12, s. 2015. Guidelines on the early language, literacy, and numeracy program: professional development component. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2015/04/10/do-12-s-2015-guidelines-on-the-early-language-literacy-and-numeracy-program-professional-development-component/>
- DepEd Order No. 74, s. 2009. Institutionalizing Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MLE). <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2009/07/14/do-74-s-2009-institutionalizing-mother-tongue-based-multilingual-education-mle/>
- DepEd Order No. 45, s. 2002. Reading Literacy Program in the Elementary Schools. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2002/09/11/do-45-s-2002-reading-literacy-program-in-the-elementary-schools/>
- Marmor, T. & Bartels, E. (2017). *Managing Language Programs, Perspectives, Processes and Practices*, SIL International.
- Ocampo, D. (2016). *K to 12 Languages Curriculum*. Pasig City: DepEd Publications.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Rustum D. Geonzon, PhD
School Division of Samar
Department of Education – Philippines